

1 **Spatial autocorrelation and host anemone species drive local components of fitness in a**
2 **wild clownfish population.**

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20 MLB, MS and SP designed the monitoring program and long-term research program on Kimbe
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23

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36

37 **Summary:** Ecological drivers of fitness components such as the lifetime reproductive success
38 (LRS) determine whether a population will be susceptible to change in its habitat. To date, only
39 few studies quantified the LRS across multiple generations in marine species, and examples
40 from the wild are missing. As a result of a long term sampling effort, such information is
41 available for the wild orange clownfish, *Amphiprion percula*, population from Kimbe Island
42 (PNG). There, little evolutionary adaptive potential was found and the LRS for the self-
43 recruiting portion of the population is mainly driven by the habitat of the breeder. However,
44 within the habitat variable, which of the host anemone species, the geographic location, the
45 density and the depth contributes to LRS remains unknown because they were combined into a
46 global habitat information. Here we tested whether it is the ecology or the spatial distribution
47 of clownfish that has the potential to shape local components of fitness and self-recruitment,
48 which are key parameters for the maintenance of this wild population. Our state of the art
49 spatially explicit analysis disentangled the role of these factors. We found that the host anemone
50 species had an impact on wild clownfish LRS independently from their spatial distribution. The
51 spatial distribution nevertheless had an impact on its own, as reflected by the spatial
52 autocorrelation of LRS. Depth and density of anemones did not show a significant impact. Our
53 findings imply that this clownfish population is susceptible to human-induced or natural
54 modifications of the proportion of the two host anemone species and their spatial distribution.

55

56 **Introduction**

57 Wild populations resilience to worldwide anthropogenic changes is closely linked to their
58 adaptive potential (Eizaguirre and Baltazar-Soares 2014). Adaptive potential, i.e., the ability of

59 species or populations to respond positively by mean of phenotypic or molecular changes to the
60 environmental demand, is an effective parameter to integrate in conservation strategies (Funk
61 et al. 2019). For instance, the efficiency of coral reef restoration is maximized when their
62 adaptive potential is known and high (Baums et al. 2019). In the wild, populations harbouring
63 adaptive potential have been shown to cope with climate change in many taxa such as plants
64 (Jordan et al. 2017), birds (Gienapp et al. 2008), mammals (Boutin and Lane 2014), fishes
65 (Muñoz et al. 2015) and corals (Matz et al. 2020). Despite its growing recognition as a critical
66 predictor of the persistence of species confronted to environmental change, the adaptive
67 potential remains rarely directly estimated in wild populations to date (Radchuk et al. 2019).

68 The adaptive potential of a population is represented by its variation in fitness that underlies its
69 ability to respond to natural selection (Fisher 1930). While inherited variation in fitness
70 increases the population microevolutionary response to selection, environmental variation in
71 fitness reduces this response (Price 1970). Assessing the relative environmental vs. genetic
72 contribution to fitness variation therefore allows identifying the mechanisms shaping the ability
73 of wild populations to adapt and to evaluate their adaptive potential. This assessment is typically
74 done by using quantitative genetic approaches to estimate genetic and environmental variance
75 components for fitness proxies (Kruuk 2004). Experimental evidence in the wild showed that
76 the Lifetime Reproductive Success (LRS), i.e., the total number of offspring recorded as
77 breeders produced by individuals over their lifetime (Hendry et al. 2018) is a good proxy for
78 the real fitness of individuals (Brommer et al. 2004). However, it remains rarely used in wild
79 populations because its measurement requires long-term datasets. It was studied in birds and
80 mammals (e.g. Kruuk et al. 2000, Mcleery et al. 2004, Teplitsky et al. 2009, Mcfarlane et al.
81 2014), and only rarely in other taxa such as insects, fish and plants (Hendry et al. 2018, Salles
82 et al. 2020).

83 Lack of knowledge on environmental and genetic variation of LRS in wild marine populations
84 is obviously problematic when considering the stakes of their adaptation to global change. This
85 is particularly true for coral reefs that are severely impacted and threatened by climate change
86 (Hughes et al. 2003, van Hooidek et al. 2016). The degradation and loss of coral reef habitats
87 affect many fish species (Jones et al. 2004). Coral reef fish populations are experiencing a
88 massive shift in selective forces that challenges their connectivity, self-recruitment, and
89 therefore their maintenance (Munday et al. 2008, 2009). Although this possibility is currently
90 unexplored by most, their adaptive potential can be evaluated in the wild in a realistic ecological
91 background. Previous work in the long-term monitored wild population of the orange clownfish

92 (*Amphiprion percula*) at Kimbe Island, Papua New Guinea, showed that it requires a demanding
93 field survey and statistical framework but that it can be achieved (Salles et al. 2020). It also
94 showed that the habitat of the breeders made the greatest contribution to LRS variation among
95 individuals (Salles et al. 2020). Overall, this work demonstrated that there was little genetic
96 variation in LRS (less than 2%) and therefore little microevolutionary adaptive potential (Salles
97 et al. 2020). Finally, the sustainability of this population is therefore mostly under the control
98 of the environment that the local breeders are experiencing.

99 Most studies investigating the genetic variation of fitness in monitored wild populations found
100 little genetic variation (Hendry et al. 2018). This is expected from populations at evolutionary
101 equilibrium when no adaptive evolution is ongoing over the rather limited timeframe of the
102 survey as compared to the timeframe of the evolution of species. In this case, little effort was
103 directed so far towards identifying the ecological mechanisms driving fitness variation. Here
104 we disentangle different ecological sources of variation in LRS in a wild coral reef fish
105 population. By doing so, our aim is also to improve the understanding of the capacity of wild
106 clownfish to maintain self-recruitment above 50%. This is crucial because the habitat of the
107 clownfish is changing and self-recruitment has been shown as a key contribution for the
108 population maintenance in the long term (Jones et al. 1999). As mentioned earlier, previous
109 study outlined that the habitat of the breeders – defined as the combination of their host
110 anemone species and the lagoon where they live – contributes most to the variation in LRS
111 (Salles et al. 2020). In the worldwide context of natural habitat degradation that also affects
112 host anemones, it is crucial to separate the role of specific interactions from other ecological
113 factors affecting clownfish survival. The relative detailed contribution of the anemone species,
114 depth and local density in anemones (three potential LRS drivers of this species) is key to
115 understanding the ecology of clownfish adaptation in their complex habitat but remains
116 unknown to date. Moreover, the spatial distribution of anemones where the fish live is not
117 homogeneous around Kimbe island. Because of this spatial heterogeneity, anemones are not
118 spatially independent so that disentangling the effects of ecological conditions (density, depth,
119 etc.) would be inappropriate if this spatial autocorrelation is unaccounted for.

120 Spatial autocorrelation can generate similarity in LRS amongst geographically close individuals
121 (Legendre 1993). Although studies on this topic remain rare, they have mainly documented
122 spatial variation in fitness proxies (Kalisz 1986, Stratton & Bennington 1998, Wilkin et al.
123 2009). For example, Wilkin et al. (2009) found spatial variation for the average mass of great
124 tit fledglings – which is a fitness proxy – in association with soil concentration in calcium in a

125 450ha woodland. Traditionally used in macro-ecological or population genetic approaches,
126 spatial autocorrelation recently gained interest for studies of fitness variation (Stopher et al.
127 2012, Marrot et al. 2015). This is because spatial autocorrelation causes pseudoreplication if
128 not taken into account, which might strongly bias statistical estimates (Haining 2003). A meta-
129 analysis conducted on 24 studies using linear regressions found on average 25% bias affecting
130 model coefficients when spatial autocorrelation was unaccounted for (Dormann 2007). For
131 instance, heritability and selection can be overestimated if spatial dependency among sampling
132 units is ignored (Stopher et al. 2012, Marrot et al. 2015, Gervais et al. 2022). Around Kimbe
133 island, similar complications may arise from the spatial distribution of anemones associated
134 with heterogeneity in depth and density by causing spatial dependency among clown fishes.

135 The aims of this study are two-folds: (i) to build a spatially explicit model estimating the effect
136 of the anemone species, local density and depth on the LRS of clownfish. To this aim, we used
137 a powerful geostatistical method that takes into account spatial autocorrelation at any spatial
138 scale to disentangle the relative contribution of these effects independently from their spatial
139 structure, and (ii) to compare this spatially explicit model to a model that does not include
140 spatial autocorrelation in order to quantify the potential bias induced by spatial dependency
141 amongst individuals on the estimates of ecological effects on LRS; we expect these effects to
142 be overestimated when spatial autocorrelation is not taken into account.

143

144 **Material & Methods**

145 *Study system*

146 A natural population of orange clownfish (*A. percula*) living on the reef surrounding Kimbe
147 Island (Fig. 1a; 5°12'22.56" S, 150°22'35.58" E), West New Britain Province of Papua New
148 Guinea, was surveyed every second year from 2003 to 2013. Here, *A. percula* lives in a
149 mutualistic association with one of two host sea anemone species, *Heteractis magnifica* and
150 *Stichodactyla gigantea*. All anemones occupied by a clownfish group have been geographically
151 located, tagged for long term monitoring and sampled every second years for a total of 310
152 anemones (176 *H. magnifica* and 134 *S. gigantea*). Within each clownfish group of typically
153 three to five individuals, there is a size-based dominance hierarchy: the female is the largest,
154 the male is the second largest, and the immatures rank progressively lower in the hierarchy as
155 they decrease in size. If the single female adult of a group dies, then the male changes sex to
156 female, and the largest immature from the anemone moves up in the hierarchy to a sexually

157 mature male. Reproduction occurs year-round, with females laying a few hundreds of eggs in a
158 clutch near the pedal disk of the host anemone each lunar month. The eggs hatch after c.a. 7
159 days of paternal care into larvae that spend c.a. 10 days in the pelagic environment (Roux et al.
160 2020) before settling into an anemone, either at their natal location (Kimbe Island) or elsewhere
161 along a declining dispersal kernel (Planes et al. 2009). On the reefs around Kimbe Island,
162 anemone positions were recorded with a GPS, and depth was measured using a dive computer.
163 Anemones were surveyed during each biannual sampling period, and all fishes within the
164 anemones were counted, captured using hand nets, measured using callipers (total length, TL),
165 and fin-clipped underwater for genetic analysis. Each fish was processed on SCUBA in situ,
166 with each individual caught, processed next to the anemone, and then released back on the same
167 anemone. The biggest fish in each anemone was identified as the female, the second largest
168 individual was assumed to be the male, and all other individuals were recorded as subadults
169 (TL, >25 mm) or new recruits (TL, <25 mm). Every sampled fish was genotyped at 22
170 polymorphic microsatellite loci (Bonin et al. 2016) and the pedigree of the population has been
171 constructed (see Salles et al. 2016 and Salles et al. 2020 for a complete description of the
172 pedigree construction of this population). The pedigree revealed half of the juveniles
173 successfully recruiting were progeny of local breeding pairs (Salles et al. 2016).

174

175 *LRS & Ecological drivers*

176 The high level of philopatry in this wild population of fish represents a rare opportunity to
177 explore variation in LRS in a marine fish with a pelagic larval stage, given the fact that most
178 estimations of LRS in the wild have been conducted in birds and mammals. Based on the
179 pedigree, the LRS of an individual has been defined as the total number of descendants
180 produced during its lifetime on a biannual basis that successfully recruited at Kimbe island.
181 Note that, contrary to most studies using LRS, our LRS measure does not refer to the number
182 of offspring produced by each individual and sampled as breeders on the following years. Here,
183 a recruit is defined as an adult (or subadult) sampled and born on the reef surrounding Kimbe
184 island. Our focus was made on the habitat of breeders and not on the habitat conditions where
185 the larvae settle, which could have an effect on the LRS of their parents. This concern should
186 however not affect our results because clownfish offspring recruited in similar proportions in
187 the two species of anemones around Kimbe island (Salles et al. 2016). Furthermore, settlement
188 habitat conditions were partially considered in the local density in anemone species within a
189 200m-radius around the parental anemone we investigated.

190 We chose to disentangle the effect of four ecological drivers: the anemone species where the
191 parents are living (called after the “focal anemone”), the density in *H. magnifica* in a 200m-
192 radius around the focal anemone, the density in *S. gigantea* in a 200m-radius around the focal
193 anemone and the depth. The micro-habitat provided by the two anemone species is remarkably
194 different in terms of shape, size and toxicity (Dunn 1981). Specifically, *H. magnifica* has larger
195 and less toxic tentacles than *S. gigantea* (Nedosyko et al. 2014). We chose to measure the
196 density of anemones in an area with a 200m-radius around the focal anemone because the spatial
197 distribution of recruits is not heterogeneous around their parents in this population, and the
198 mean distance between self-recruits and their parents was equal to 254m (\pm 189m), with 47%
199 of recruits located at less than 200m from their parents (Supplementary information 1). This
200 mean distance between recruits and their parents was significantly different (Wilcox test *P*-
201 value < 0.001) from the mean distance between each anemone occupied by a self-recruit and
202 the other anemones in this population (388m \pm 37m), suggesting a potential effect of the local
203 environment around the focal anemone on the probability of self-recruiting (Jones et al., 2005;
204 Buston et al., 2012). We chose to investigate depth as a potential driver because the two
205 anemones species are not equally distributed across depth (Fig. 1B, 1C) with *H. magnifica* more
206 likely found in deeper lagoon waters (4.10m \pm 2.61) than *S. gigantea*, which is found closer to
207 shore (1.34m \pm 0.51). Moreover, because larvae may recruit on deeper anemones than their
208 anemones of birth (Buston et al. 2012), we expected that the probability to produce self-recruits
209 increases as the depth of parental anemones decreases, independently from the species of the
210 anemone.

211

212 *Statistical analysis*

213 All statistical analyses were carried out using the R software (v. 4.0.3). Individual LRS followed
214 a Poisson statistical distribution with a mean of 1.27 (\pm 2.32) and a maximum of 20 self-recruits
215 per individual. Because the statistical distribution of individual LRS included an excess of zero
216 (58% of individuals did not produce self-recruits in the population), we chose to test for the
217 effect of ecological drivers by using a zero-inflated model. In this type of model, the excess of
218 zero is analysed by a separate process (the probability that fish will not produce self-recruits,
219 because in a zero-inflated model, it is the probability to have a zero that is estimated, generally
220 with a logit link function) from the count values (the number of self-recruits produced by
221 breeders, generally with a log link function). This choice was corroborated by a smaller Akaike
222 information criterion (AIC) of a null zero-inflated model (AIC=4246) than the AIC of a null
223 generalized linear model following a Poisson distribution (AIC=5423). We included in the

224 model the first year of sampling of each fish to take into account the lifespan on LRS. Although
225 this variable is an incomplete proxy of lifespan, it is equally spatially distributed in the
226 population, preventing it from affecting the spatial distribution of LRS.
227 Because no ecological variables was expected to predominantly affect the probability to
228 produce at least one recruit or the number of recruits produced, we used a model-averaging
229 approach (Grueber et al. 2011, Symonds and Moussalli 2011). Contrary to the traditional single-
230 inference approach based on P -value, the model averaging aims to test multiple hypotheses in
231 the same analysis using the AIC (Akaike 1974). This approach is particularly indicated for our
232 purpose because we also had no prior expectation about which component of LRS (the
233 probability that fish will not produce a self-recruit or the number of self-recruits produced by
234 breeders) would be affected by our five variables (lifespan and the four ecological variables).
235 The model-averaging method is based on three steps: (i) the generation of all possible sub-
236 models from the set of predictors of interest. Here our zero-inflated model included ten
237 variables (the effect of our five variables on the probability that fish will not produce a self-
238 recruit and the count number of recruits produced by breeders), leading to 1032 models
239 generated. (ii) The selection of the AIC-based 95% best models (leading to 106 spatially explicit
240 models and 13 non-spatial models, see geostatistics below). (iii) The averaging of estimates of
241 predictors among all selected models weighted by Akaike weight of each model that include
242 the corresponding predictor. We calculated the relative importance and the confidence intervals
243 associated with each predictor. This relative importance can be interpreted as the probability
244 that the variable of interest is a component of the best model (Symonds and Moussalli 2011).
245 Following Galipaud et al. (2014), we considered that an ecological variable significantly affects
246 the probability that fish will not produce a self-recruit or the count number of self-recruits
247 produced by breeders when the confidence intervals of its averaged estimate do not overlap 0.
248 The model-averaging analysis was conducted using the *MuMIn* (Barton 2009) package in R.

249

250 *Geostatistics*

251 The visualization of the spatial distribution of the LRS suggested that this variable is not
252 homogeneous across space (Fig. 1A). Before conducting geostatistical analyses, we formally
253 tested if LRS was significantly spatially autocorrelated around Kimbe island by using spatial
254 correlograms. Our analysis revealed a significant and positive spatial autocorrelation at 230m
255 and 460m and a significant negative spatial autocorrelation at 690m and 920m (Fig. 2A). This
256 result indicated that LRS is not spatially independent and geostatistical modelling is required
257 to disentangle the effect of the ecological drivers. Based on the abundant literature that compare

258 the performance of different geostatistical methods (Dormann et al. 2007, Kissling and Carl
259 2008, Beguería and Pueyo 2009, Bini et al. 2009, Diniz-Filho et al. 2009, Beale et al. 2010,
260 Marrot et al. 2015), we chose to use the Principal Coordinates of Neighbourhood Matrix
261 (PCNM) approach (Dray et al. 2006). The general principle of the PCNM is based on the
262 extraction of eigenvectors from a truncated distance matrix among spatial units. Each of these
263 eigenvectors (called after “Egs”) describes a specific spatial scale (regarding the spatial
264 distribution of sampling units) and can be subsequently added as a covariate in any statistical
265 model to model the spatial structure of the response variable (Borcard and Legendre 2002). The
266 use of the PCNM approach can be decomposed in four steps: (i) Compute a truncated pairwise
267 Euclidean distance matrix between spatial units. (ii) Perform principal coordinate analysis of
268 the distance matrix and extract the corresponding eigenvectors (Egs) for a total number of Egs
269 equal to the number of sampling units (302 clownfish with non-null LRS at Kimbe island).
270 Although the whole set of Egs describes the whole spatial structure of the dataset, it is not
271 possible to include all Egs in any model without over-parameterizing it. (iii) Select a subset of
272 Egs to include as covariates in any model. This part of the analysis is crucial and strategies to
273 select Egs are diversified (Blanchet et al. 2008). Here we chose to conduct a backward-forward
274 selection based on AIC (Ficetola and Padoa-schioppa 2009) to select the best set of Egs that
275 explains spatial variation in LRS. This selection led us to keep 29 Egs. This set of Egs
276 represented the minimum number of Egs necessary to describe spatial variation in LRS. (iv)
277 Include the set of selected Egs in any model to take into account spatial autocorrelation between
278 units of sampling. Here we included the set of 29 Egs as covariate in the zero-inflated model-
279 averaging procedure: all the possible sub-models generated from the set of predictors of interest
280 in step 1 of the model-averaging included the 29 Egs. Finally, in order to quantify the biases
281 induced by spatial autocorrelation when it was ignored, we compared a spatially explicit zero-
282 inflated model-averaging procedure (including the 29 Egs) to a “naïve” zero-inflated model-
283 averaging procedure. Specifically, we compared the sign, the absolute value and the confidence
284 intervals associated with each averaged estimate.

285

286 **Results**

287

288 *Strong spatial autocorrelation*

289 Spatial autocorrelation detected in LRS (Fig. 2A) was totally removed by the set of 29 Egs
290 selected by the PCNM method (Fig. 2B). We added this set of Egs as covariate in the zero-

291 inflated model averaging procedure and we compared it with a naïve model. The averaged
292 estimates, their confidence intervals and relative importance are summarised for the non-spatial
293 and the spatially explicit model averaging analyses in Table 1. The inclusion of Egs affected
294 the magnitude, the sign and the confidence intervals of averaged estimates both in terms of
295 probability of not self-recruiting and the count number of recruits produced (Table 1). Detailed
296 results for each parameter are described below.

297

298 *Non spatial and spatially explicit model comparison*

299 The comparison between a non-spatial full model (including all variables) and a spatially
300 explicit full model (including all variables and the set of 29 Egs) revealed that the inclusion of
301 Egs significantly increased the degree of fit of the model with an improvement of adjusted R^2
302 of 0.18 (the non-spatial and the spatially explicit model explained respectively 16% and 34%
303 of the variance in LRS) and a drop of AIC of 183. This AIC drop means that the inclusion of
304 the 29 Egs significantly improved the degree of fit of the model without over-parameterizing
305 the model, therefore insuring that no more parameters were defined than can be estimated from
306 the data.

307

308 *Year of sampling effect*

309 In both non-spatial and spatially explicit model-averaging approaches, the year of first sampling
310 (first year sampling) increased the probability to not self-recruit and in the presence of self-
311 recruitment decreased the number of recruits with the same magnitude (Table 1). This means
312 that earliest sampled fishes had the highest probability to produce at least one self-recruit and
313 produced also more self-recruits than late sampled fishes because mathematically, the
314 monitoring period is more likely to overlap with the full lifespan of fish sampled earlier, which
315 increases the probability to produce a self-recruit that we had the opportunity to sample.

316

317 *Ecological effect on LRS components*

318 The probability that fish will not produce a self-recruit (represented by the logarithm of the
319 odds ratio; which estimate and 95% confidence interval are presented between brackets) was
320 significantly affected by the focal anemone species (-0.592 [-0.999 ; -0.185] for breeders living
321 on *S. gigantea*) in the spatially explicit model-averaging approach. Interestingly, this was also
322 the case in the non-spatial model-averaging approach where the probability that fish will not
323 produce a self-recruit was significantly affected by the focal anemone species (-0.511 [-0.809 ;

324 -0.213]) for breeders living on *S. gigantea*, and the 200m-radius density in *H. magnifica* (-0.117
325 [-0.280 ; -0.011]).

326

327 We back transformed the results of the spatially explicit model from the latent (inferred through
328 the model link function) to the observed scale for the sake of clarity. Fish living on *S. gigantea*
329 had odds to not produce a self-recruit lowered by half ($\exp(-0.592) = 0.553$), and therefore twice
330 the odds to produce a self-recruit, in comparison to those living on *H. magnifica*. While 56%
331 of fish did not self-recruit in the population, this proportion was down to 41% on *S. gigantea*.

332

333 The other component of LRS, which was the number of recruits produced by breeders, was not
334 affected by the anemone species and the density in the spatially explicit model. It is interesting
335 to note that it was however significantly affected by the focal anemone species (0.365 [0.233 ;
336 0.496] for breeders living on *S. gigantea*) and the 200m-radius density in both anemone species
337 (0.119 [0.059 ; 0.179] and 0.127 [0.066 ; 0.187] for the density in *S. gigantea* and *H. magnifica*
338 respectively) in the non-spatial model averaging, here again emphasizing some effect of spatial
339 auto-correlation that is not taken into account in traditional analyses.

340

341 **Discussion**

342 Our spatially explicit analysis of a unique combination of long-term data from a monitored wild
343 clownfish population which pedigree and individual geographic location are known revealed
344 two main results: (i) When ignored, spatial autocorrelation strongly affected the estimates of
345 our zero-inflated model-averaging procedure, leading to serious biological misinterpretations.
346 (ii) Breeders living on *S. gigantea* contributed to a larger extent to the self-recruitment of the
347 population than those living on *H. magnifica*, and this effect was independent from the local
348 density, the depth and the spatial structure.

349

350 *Why use a spatially explicit approach?*

351 Beyond taking into account the spatial structure of clownfish LRS to identify its ecological
352 drivers independently from spatial effects, our study aimed at evaluating the consequences of
353 not accounting for spatial autocorrelation. We successfully removed spatial dependency at all
354 scales in LRS by using the PCNM approach. This method presents numerous advantages: it
355 allows to control for spatial autocorrelation at any scale, it does not need the assumption of
356 stationary (spatial autocorrelation does not depend on direction) and isotropy (spatial

357 autocorrelation is constant across the study site), and it can be incorporated with any statistical
358 models commonly used by ecologists (Borcard and Legendre 2002). The inclusion of Egs
359 doubled the variance explained in the LRS at Kimbe island (the non-spatial and the spatially
360 explicit model explained respectively 16% and 34% of the variance in LRS, Table 1),
361 suggesting that unaccounted spatially autocorrelated variables affect the LRS. Note however
362 that although the variance explained by a model including only the ecological variables
363 explained 16% of the variation in LRS, it is incorrect to attribute 18% of variation explained by
364 the Egs because ecological variables and Egs explained shared variation in LRS. Moreover, a
365 model including only the set of Egs explained 27% of the variation in LRS (not shown in Table
366 1).

367

368 The comparison of the non-spatial and the spatially explicit model-averaging procedure
369 including the Egs revealed that, when unaccounted for, spatial autocorrelation biased the
370 absolute values of estimates and their confidence intervals. This result was not surprising and
371 confirmed a large body of evidence, both on simulated and real data, showing the effect of
372 spatial autocorrelation on estimates (e.g. Lennon 2000, Dormann 2007, Beale et al. 2010, Le
373 Rest et al. 2013). As pseudoreplication, spatial autocorrelation decreases the precision
374 (increasing the type 1 error) around estimates and alters (in a non-predictable way) their
375 absolute values when unaccounted for if the response and the explicative variables are spatially
376 autocorrelated (Beale et al. 2010). In our analysis, only the effect of life span (the first sampling
377 year) on LRS was unaffected by spatial autocorrelation. This result was not surprising since the
378 life span was not expected to be spatially structured around Kimbe island. Among the ecological
379 variables, three of them had their confidence intervals overlapping 0 (for both LRS components)
380 when spatial autocorrelation was taken into account. Beyond statistical considerations, these
381 results highlight how spatial autocorrelation can result in serious biological misinterpretations
382 when unaccounted for. For example, while a non-spatial analysis would conclude that wild
383 clownfish surrounded by a high density in anemone (within a 200m-radius) produce more
384 recruits than those living in empty areas, our spatially explicit model did not detect any effect
385 of the density in anemones.

386

387 *Spatial autocorrelation of LRS*

388 Our results showed that there was a spatial structure of self-recruitment around Kimbe island.
389 This is in line with a previous study conducted in the same clownfish population where it was
390 suggested that the location of the lagoon could influence LRS (Salles et al. 2020). Our approach

391 allowed us to go further and detected a strong spatial autocorrelation of LRS. As mentioned
392 earlier, it would be inappropriate to try and to provide a precise estimate of its strength. This
393 effect occurred over a relatively small spatial scale (less than 1km). This is an original result
394 because spatial autocorrelation is a property of ecosystems and can be found at any scale, from
395 micrometres to the continental scale (Legendre 1993), but it was mainly investigated by
396 ecologists interested in macro-ecological patterns at very large scales (Dormann 2007) and
397 population geneticists estimating the limits of dispersal within and between populations (Sokal
398 et al. 1989, Vekemans and Hardy 2004). It was in fact rarely investigated in studies exploring
399 individual fitness variation. There is only few evidence in wild plant and animal populations
400 that spatial autocorrelation can strongly impact the estimation of natural selection (Marrot et al.
401 2015, 2022), estimates of genetic variation for fitness-related traits (Stopher et al. 2012, Gervais
402 et al. 2022) and now ecological drivers of LRS with this study.

403 One limitation of our spatial analysis comes from the Euclidean distances that we used.
404 Euclidean distances likely may not accurately represent connectivity in the ocean, where islands
405 and currents can impede routes of travelling larvae (Trembl et al. 2008). Oceanic distances
406 accounting for actual currents around the island would be a good alternative to Euclidean
407 distances (White et al. 2010, Truelove et al. 2017) because currents are generally predicted to
408 have a strong effect on dispersal pattern (Cowen et al. 2000, but see Van Wynsberge et al.
409 2017). They would likely help to explain the variation of LRS more accurately. Our results have
410 to be interpreted with caution since currents and the role of the island of Kimbe were not
411 considered in our spatially-explicit analysis of LRS. One should note that a previous study
412 showed that this currents were likely not influencing self-recruitment at short distances of about
413 one kilometer around Kimbe island (Buston et al. 2012) although at the broader scale of Kimbe
414 bay, a direct relationship was found between geographic distance and genetic differentiation
415 (Pinsky et al. 2017). Furthermore, although not explicitly modelled, the potential role of the
416 island was at least partially taken into account by the PCNM method because it estimates
417 patterns of spatial autocorrelation at any scale (Borcard and Legendre 2002).

418

419 *The host anemone species affects clownfish LRS*

420 Our spatially explicit approach allowed us to identify some ecological drivers of wild *A. percula*
421 clownfish LRS without potentially confounding their effect with spatial effects. Our results
422 confirmed the findings from a previous study (Salles et al. 2020) conducted on the same
423 clownfish population: an important part of variation in components of fitness linked to self-

424 recruitment was explained by the ecological conditions of the habitat of breeders. Our approach
425 allowed us to go further and disentangle the relative contribution of different ecological factors.
426 Among them, we demonstrated that the anemone species is the only factor affecting the LRS.
427 Specifically, we found a higher probability to produce at least one recruit for breeders living in
428 *S. gigantea* than those living in *H. magnifica*. The spatially explicit approach revealed that this
429 effect was independent from the depth, the local density in anemones around the focal anemone,
430 and the spatial structure of the population, suggesting a direct causal relationship between the
431 anemone species and LRS.

432

433 Experiments will be necessary to identify the causal mechanism linking the anemone species
434 to the variation in LRS that we observed in wild populations. **Several** hypotheses can be
435 assessed to explain our finding. First, one may push forward the lower clownfish fecundity
436 caused by hormonal stress resulting from host anemone bleaching (Beldade et al. 2017) as a
437 potential explanation of our results if anemone bleaching affected differentially the two
438 anemone species. However, anemone bleaching cannot explain our results because this
439 phenomenon is supposed to affect all anemone species with the same magnitude (Hobbs et al.
440 2013) and no anemone bleaching event was reported over the duration of the survey. Second,
441 one candidate hypothesis to explain the higher LRS of clownfish living on *S. gigantea* is that
442 this anemone species is more toxic than *H. magnifica* (Nedosyko et al. 2014), which could offer
443 more protection to clownfish, and ultimately affect positively its fitness because of a higher
444 survival. This higher survival would increase the life expectancy of breeders and therefore their
445 opportunity to produce self-recruits. Third, along with this difference in protection allocated to
446 clownfish, female size may vary (Buston 2004) as it is mediated by the group size which has
447 been shown to be driven by the size and shape of the anemone (Chausson et al. 2018). A direct
448 link can be drawn to a recent study on *A. percula* (Barbasch et al. 2020), using both
449 experimental design and field work data, which revealed a strong and positive relationship
450 between anemone area, clownfish size, and reproductive success, driven by food availability.
451 Whether *S. gigantea* provides clownfish with a higher food availability remains however to be
452 tested. Observations in the field nevertheless suggest that clownfish spend more time feeding
453 out and above *S. gigantea* anemones than clownfish hosted by *H. magnifica* (S. Planes personal
454 observation).

455

456 The host anemone species, whether through their toxicity, size or available food, or other
457 unknown features, directly influences wild clownfish self-recruitment, and thereby their ability

458 to locally replenish the population around Kimbe island. Any changes to the ecology of the
459 anemone species would therefore impact the sustainability of the clownfish population. The
460 limits of the perspective on clownfish sustainability provided by our finding is restricted to the
461 frontiers of the local population. Broader consequences cannot be revealed by our investigation
462 of the local component of the clownfish lifetime reproductive success. Whether an integrative
463 perspective considering long distance dispersal would reveal a trade-off between a breeder's
464 ability to produce self-recruits and successful settlers on foreign anemones remains unknown
465 to date.

466

467 *Conclusion*

468 Ecological conditions experienced by wild clownfish are undoubtedly strongly impacting
469 components fitness linked to self-recruitment such as the LRS. Our study revealed how crucial
470 it is to account for spatial autocorrelation to disentangle ecological sources of variation from
471 confounding spatial effects and prevent biological misinterpretation. Geostatistical models such
472 as PCNM represent a powerful tool to identify the spatial autocorrelation of LRS, even at small
473 spatial scale. In a context of worldwide threat on coral reefs (Hughes et al. 2003, van Hooijdonk
474 et al. 2016), it is crucial to investigate the sources of individual variation in LRS to predict the
475 resilience of wild coral reef fish populations. As part of a marine reserve (Almany et al. 2007),
476 the lagoons around Kimbe island where wild clownfish are monitored are protected from
477 fishery or direct habitat degradation and this clownfish population has proven to persist in
478 absence of migrants (Salles et al. 2015). However, our study revealed that the subsistence of
479 the population could be altered if the proportion of *S. gigantea* was to change independently
480 from density, depth and other environmental aspects and a similar concern could be raised if
481 the spatial distribution of anemone species was to change. More investigations are required
482 before one may claim that climate change will affect the adaptive potential of wild clownfish
483 around Kimbe Island through its effect on the spatial distribution of anemone species.
484 Furthermore, at a broader geographic scale, the mechanisms underlying the balance between
485 selfrecruitment and long distance dispersal in interaction with host anemone choice and
486 availability are only partially known to date.

487

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500

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726 Table 1: Zero-inflated non-spatial vs. spatially explicit model averaged estimates based on a
 727 model averaging conducted on 1032 models (see method). The probability to not self-recruit is
 728 represented by the logarithms of the odds ratios. RI represent the relative importance of each
 729 variable. Anemone species: *S. gigantea* represents the effect of living on *S. gigantea* compared
 730 to *H. magnifica*. Density 200m *S. gigantea* and Density 200m *H. magnifica* represent
 731 respectively the effect of the density in *S. gigantea* and *H. magnifica* in a 200m-radius around
 732 the focal anemone. In bold the variables with confidence intervals that do not overlap 0.

	Non-spatial model-averaging			Spatial model-averaging (including Eggs)		
	Estimates	Confidence intervals	RI	Estimates	Confidence intervals	RI
<i>Probability to not self-recruit</i>						
Intercept	0.375	0.191; 0.558	-	0.243	0.028; 0.457	-
First year sampling	0.433	0.291; 0.576	100%	0.469	0.313; 0.626	100%
Depth	0.002	-0.148; 0.165	28%	-0.062	-0.284; 0.160	27%
Anemone species: <i>S. gigantea</i>	-0.511	-0.809; -0.213	99%	-0.592	-0.999; -0.185	99%
Density 200m <i>S. gigantea</i>	0.018	-0.078; 0.191	34%	0.060	-0.124; 0.245	25%
Density 200m <i>H. magnifica</i>	-0.117	-0.280; -0.011	77%	-0.023	-0.201; 0.154	25%
<i>Number of recruits produced</i>						
Intercept	0.740	0.643; 0.837	-	0.806	0.722; 0.891	-
First year sampling	-0.309	-0.386; -0.232	100%	-0.247	-0.326; -0.169	100%
Depth	0.008	-0.050; 0.104	32%	0.009	-0.075; 0.094	25%
Anemone species: <i>S. gigantea</i>	0.365	0.233; 0.496	100%	-0.045	-0.218; 0.129	27%
Density 200m <i>S. gigantea</i>	0.119	0.059; 0.179	100%	0.068	-0.008; 0.145	63%
Density 200m <i>H. magnifica</i>	0.127	0.066; 0.187	100%	0.067	-0.009; 0.143	60%
<i>Degree of fit of the full model (including all variables)</i>						
Adjusted R ²		0.16			0.34	
AIC		4042			3859	

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735

736 Figure 1: Spatial distribution of the mean LRS (A, averaged among all breeding fishes living
 737 on the same anemone), the depth (B) and the anemone species (C). Each point represents an
 738 anemone for a total of 302 anemones sampled at Kimbe island.

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741 Figure 2: Moran's I correlogram for LRS at Kimbe island (with associated standard deviations)
 742 before (A) and after (B) correcting for spatial autocorrelation with the Egs selected by the
 743 PCNM (see method). Moran's index was calculated at 4 distance classes, from 230m to 920m,
 744 with a distance lag of 230m. There is a significant and positive spatial autocorrelation at 230m
 745 and 460m and a significant negative spatial autocorrelation at 690m and 920m in LRS before
 746 correcting for spatial autocorrelation (A). Spatial autocorrelation was undetected in LRS after
 747 correcting with the PCs (B).

748

749 Supplementary information 1: Statistical distribution of the mean distance between each
750 anemone and the other (A) and the distance between self-recruits and their parents (B) at Kimbe
751 island. Red dotted lines represent the mean of each statistical distribution (A: 383m ± 38m; B:
752 237m ± 183m). Based on a Wilcoxon test, these two statistical distributions were significantly
753 different ($P < 0.001$). Note that 55% of self-recruits were located at less than 200m from their
754 parents.

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